

A 178bp diagnostic D-loop fragment (OvisCR) to discriminate domestic sheep (*Ovis aries*) and European mouflon (*Ovis musimon*) in diet metabarcoding studies

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Supplementary Material 1. DNA quantification protocols.

A quantitative PCR (qPCR) was performed to quantify PCR products used for metabarcoding analyses before pooling libraries and purification. The qPCR was performed with EvaGreen qPCR Master Mix (Solis BioDyne) on a Bio-Rad CFX96 Touch Real-Time PCR Detection System. Each 10 μ L reaction contained 2 μ L of 5 \times EvaGreen Master Mix, 0.2 μ M of each sequencing primer, and 2 μ L of a 1:1,000,000 (10^{-6}) dilution of the PCR product. Thermal cycling conditions were as follows: an initial denaturation at 95°C for 12 min, followed by 40 cycles of 95°C for 15 s, 60°C for 20 s, and 72°C for 20 s. Fluorescence was measured at the end of each extension step. A melt curve analysis was performed to verify amplification specificity.

Following adapter ligation and purification, the concentration of each library was assessed using digital PCR (dPCR). For assay calibration, a series of eight dilutions was prepared for each library: the first two dilutions at a 1:100 ratio, followed by six successive 1:4 serial dilutions.

Digital PCR was performed using the Qiacuity EG PCR Mastermix (QIAGEN) on the Qiacuity Digital PCR System, according to the manufacturer's protocol for genotyping assays on a Qiacuity Nanoplate 26k. Each 44 μ L reaction mixture contained 14.7 μ L of 1 \times Qiacuity EG PCR Mastermix, 0.4 μ M of each sequencing primer, and 11 μ L of diluted library DNA.

Thermal cycling conditions were as follows: an initial denaturation at 95°C for 2 min, followed by 40 cycles of 95°C for 15 s, 60°C for 15 s, and 72°C for 20 s, with a final extension at 40°C for 5 min.

Priming settings were configured using the QIAGEN Priming Profile for EvaGreen. Imaging was performed using the green detection channel with an exposure time of 200 ms and a gain setting of 3.

Supplementary Material 2. Functions and parameters used in the metabarcoding pipelines.

OTUs identification with OBITools

This script was adapted from the pipeline provided on the OBITools website “*Wolves’ diet based on DNA metabarcoding*” (<https://pythonhosted.org/OBITools/wolves.html>)

```
#####
# OBITools metabarcoding pipeline (R implementation using system calls)
#####

# Path to OBITools executables
OBITOOLS <- "/path/to/obitools/"

#####
# 1. Demultiplexing and primer filtering (ngsfilter)
#####
# Assign reads to samples based on tag combinations and primer sequences.
# Reads that cannot be assigned are written to a separate file.
cmd_ngsfilter <- paste0(
  OBITOOLS,
  "ngsfilter -e 3 ",
  "-t ngsfilter_table.txt ", # A tab-delimited or space-delimited file specifying sample identifiers, primer
                           # sequences, and
                           # tag structure, used by ngsfilter to demultiplex sequencing reads.
  "-u unidentified_reads.fastq ",
  "input_reads.fastq ",    # Raw sequencing reads in FASTQ format generated by the sequencing
                           # platform.
  "> assigned_reads.fastq"
)
system(cmd_ngsfilter)

#####
# 2. Dereplication of sequences (obiuniq)
#####
# Collapse identical sequences while preserving read counts and sample origin.
cmd_obiuniq <- paste0(
  OBITOOLS,
  "obiuniq -m sample ",
  "assigned_reads.fastq ",
  "> assigned_reads.uniq.fasta"
)
system(cmd_obiuniq)

#####
# 3. Annotation of sequence metadata (obiannotate)
#####
# Add read count, sample distribution, and sequence length to FASTA headers.
cmd_obiannotate <- paste0(
  OBITOOLS,
  "obiannotate -k count -k merged_sample --length ",
  "assigned_reads.uniq.fasta ",
  "> $$ ; mv $$ assigned_reads.uniq.fasta "
```

```

)
system(cmd_obiannotate)

#####
# 4. Filtering by sequence length and abundance (obigrep)
#####
# Parameters
min_length <- 60      # set to 60 for 12S and 100 for OvisCR
max_length <- 200     # set to NA for 12S and 200 for OvisCR
min_count  <- 10      # set to 10

if (is.na(max_length)) {
  cmd_obigrep <- paste0(
    OBITOOLS,
    "obigrep ",
    "-l ", min_length ,
    "-p 'count >=' ", min_count, "",
    "assigned_reads.uniq.fasta ",
    "> assigned_reads.filtered.fasta"
  )
} else {
  cmd_obigrep <- paste(
    OBITOOLS,
    "obigrep",
    "-l", min_length,
    "-L", max_length,
    "-p 'count >=' ", min_count, "",
    "assigned_reads.uniq.fasta",
    "> assigned_reads.filtered.fasta",
    sep = ""
  )
}
system(cmd_obigrep)

#####
# 5. PCR/sequencing error removal (obiclean)
#####

# Relative abundance threshold
relative_abundance <- 0.05

# Classify sequences as head/internal/singleton and retain validated variants.
cmd_obiclean <- paste(
  OBITOOLS,
  "obiclean",
  "-s merged_sample",
  "-r", relative_abundance,
  "-H",
  "assigned_reads.filtered.fasta",
  "> assigned_reads.filtered.clean.fasta",
  sep = ""
)

```

```

system(cmd_obiclean)

#####
# 6. Conversion to tabular format (obitab)
#####

# Export curated sequence variants to a tab-delimited file.
cmd_obitab <- paste(
  OBITOOLS,
  "obitab -o",
  "assigned_reads.filtered.clean.fasta",
  "> assigned_reads.filtered.clean.tab",
  sep = ""
)
system(cmd_obitab)

#####
# End of OBITools pipeline
#####

ASVs identification with DADA2
#####
# DADA2 amplicon sequence variant (ASV) inference pipeline
# Executed entirely in R
#####

library(dada2)

# Path to OBITools executables
OBITOOLS <- "/path/to/obitools/"

#####
# 1. Demultiplexing and primer filtering (ngsfilter in OBITools)
#####
# Assign reads to samples based on tag combinations and primer sequences.
# Reads that cannot be assigned are written to a separate file.
cmd_ngsfilter <- paste(
  OBITOOLS,
  "ngsfilter -e 3",
  "-t ngsfilter_table.txt", # A tab-delimited or space-delimited file specifying sample identifiers, primer
                           # sequences, and
                           # tag structure, used by ngsfilter to demultiplex sequencing reads.
  "-u unidentified_reads.fastq",
  "input_reads.fastq",    # Raw sequencing reads in FASTQ format generated by the sequencing
                           # platform.
  "> assigned_reads.fastq",
  sep = ""
)
system(cmd_ngsfilter)

#####

```

```

# 2. Quality filtering and trimming
#####
out_filt <- filterAndTrim(
  fn = assigned_fastq_files,
  filt = filtered_fastq_files,
  trimLeft = 0,
  truncLen = 0,
  maxN = 0,
  maxEE = 3,
  truncQ = 2,
  rm.phix = TRUE,
  compress = TRUE,
  multithread = FALSE
)

#####
# 3. Error rate learning
#####
err <- learnErrors(filtered_fastq_files, multithread = TRUE)

#####
# 4. Dereplication of reads
#####
derep <- derepFastq(filtered_fastq_files, verbose = TRUE)
names(derep) <- sample_names

#####
# 5. ASV inference (denoising)
#####
dada_out <- dada(
  derep,
  err = err,
  HOMOPOLYMER_GAP_PENALTY = -1,
  BAND_SIZE = 32,
  multithread = FALSE
)

#####
# 6. Construction of ASV table
#####
seqtab <- makeSequenceTable(dada_out)

#####
# 7. Chimera removal
#####
seqtab_nochim <- removeBimeraDenovo(
  seqtab,
  method = "consensus",
  multithread = TRUE,
  verbose = TRUE
)

```

```

#####
# 8. ASV abundance and length filtering
#####
# Parameters
l_min <- 60 # set to 60 for 12S and 100 for OvisCR
l_max <- 200 # set to NA for 12S and 200 for OvisCR
count_min <- 1 # set to 1

asv_sequences <- colnames(seqtab_nochim)
asv_lengths <- nchar(asv_sequences)
asv_counts <- colSums(seqtab_nochim)

keep <- asv_lengths >= l_min &
  ifelse(is.na(l_max), TRUE, asv_lengths <= l_max) &
  asv_counts >= count_min

seqtab_filt <- seqtab_nochim[, keep, drop = FALSE]

#####
# 9. Export ASVs to OBITools-like tabular format
#####
final_tab <- data.frame(
  id = sprintf("%s:%09d", Run, seq_len(ncol(seqtab_filt))),
  count = colSums(seqtab_filt),
  seq_len = nchar(colnames(seqtab_filt)),
  sequence = colnames(seqtab_filt),
  stringsAsFactors = FALSE
)

write.table(
  final_tab,
  file = "ASV_DADA2.clean.tab",
  sep = "\t",
  quote = FALSE,
  row.names = FALSE
)

#####
# End of DADA2 pipeline
#####

```

Taxonomic assignment with BLASTn

Curated unique sequences (OTUs or ASVs) were exported as FASTA files (QUERY.fasta) containing sequence identifiers and nucleotide sequences. These files were used as queries for BLASTn searches against internal and external reference databases.

```

#####
# BLASTn taxonomic assignment pipeline
# Internal reference database + external NCBI database
# Executed from R using system() calls
#####

```

```
BLAST <- "/path/to/blast+"
WGET <- "/usr/bin/wget"
```

```
#####
# 1. Creation of internal reference database (curated haplotypes)
#####
# OVisCR_ref_database.fasta contains OvisCR reference haplotypes
cmd_make_db_internal <- paste(
  BLAST,
  "makeblastdb",
  "-in OVisCR_ref_database.fasta",
  "-dbtype nucl",
  "-out Base_Internal",
  "-blastdb_version 4",
  sep = ""
)
system(cmd_make_db_internal)
```

```
#####
# 2. Downloading external reference database taxonomy (NCBI nt)
#####
```

```
# Download the taxonomic reference (if needed)
cmd_download_ncbi <- paste(
  WGET,
  "wget ftp://ftp.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/blast/db/taxdb.tar.gz -q",
  sep = ""
)
system(cmd_download_ncbi)
```

```
# Uncompress
system("tar -zxf taxdb.tar.gz")
system("rm taxdb.tar.gz")
```

```
#####
# 3. BLASTn search against internal reference
#####
```

```
query_fasta <- "QUERY.fasta"
blast_internal_out <- "BLAST_internal.csv"
```

```
cmd_blast_internal <- paste(
  BLAST,
  "blastn -query", query_fasta,
  "-db Base_Internal",
  '-outfmt "6 qaccver saccver pident length mismatch gapopen qstart qend sstart send evaluate bitscore
  stitle"',
  ">", blast_internal_out,
```

```

sep = ""
)
system(cmd_blast_internal)

#####
# 4. BLASTn search against external NCBI nt database
#####

blast_ncbi_out <- "BLAST_NCBI.csv"

cmd_blast_ncbi <- paste(
  BLAST,
  "blastn -query", query_fasta,
  "-db nt",
  '-outfmt "6 qaccver saccver ssciname staxid pident length mismatch gapopen qstart qend sstart
send qcovus evalue bitscore stitle"',
  "-max_target_seqs 100 -remote",
  ">", blast_ncbi_out,
  sep = ""
)
system(cmd_blast_ncbi)

#####
# 5. Post-processing (internal)
#####

blast_int <- read.table(
  blast_internal_out,
  sep = "\t",
  header = FALSE,
  stringsAsFactors = FALSE
)
colnames(blast_int) <- c(
  "query_id", "subject_id", "pident", "alignment_length",
  "mismatch", "gapopen", "qstart", "qend",
  "sstart", "send", "evalue", "bitscore", "subject_title"
)

# Optional: keep high-confidence matches only
blast_int_filt <- blast_int %>%
  dplyr::filter(pident >= 97, alignment_length >= 0.8 * max(alignment_length))

write.csv(
  blast_int_filt,
  file = "BLAST_internal.filtered.csv",
  row.names = FALSE
)

#####
# 6. Post-processing (NCBI external)
#####

```

```
blast_ext <- read.table(
  blast_ncbi_out,
  sep = "\t",
  header = FALSE,
  stringsAsFactors = FALSE
)
colnames(blast_ext) <- c(
  "query_id", "subject_id", "ssci_name", "taxid",
  "pident", "length", "mismatch", "gapopen", "qstart", "qend",
  "sstart", "send", "qcovus", "evaluate", "bitscore", "subject_title"
)

# Optional: remove hits corresponding to chromosomal / transcript sequences
blast_ext_clean <- subset(blast_ext,
  !grepl("chromosome|transcript", subject_title, ignore.case = TRUE))

write.csv(
  blast_ext_clean,
  file = "BLAST_NCBI.filtered.csv",
  row.names = FALSE
)
```

Supplementary Material 4. TCS haplotype network based on a 674 bp D-loop fragment, constructed from 30 *Ovis musimon* and 41 *Ovis aries* reference samples collected in France. Each haplotype is represented by a circle for *O. aries* and a circle enclosed within a square for *O. musimon*. Each tick mark on the lines connecting the haplotypes indicates a single mutation. The circle size is proportional to the number of individuals sharing that haplotype, and the colors indicate the species.

